

FACILE SYNTHESIS OF SULFONATED POLYIMIDE WITH HIGHLY CONDUCTIVE SILVER ELECTRODE VIA DIRECT ION-EXCHANGE SELF-METALLIZATION FOR ELECTRO-ACTIVE ARTIFICIAL MUSCLE

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1 Introduction

Ionic polymer metal composites (IPMCs), one of the most promising electro-active polymers, have received much attention in the past decade due to various potential applications in artificial muscles, sensors and actuators, biomimetic robots, space and underwater applications [1-5] based on their attractive advantages of large strain, light weight, flexibility, low power consumption, biomimetic actuation, easy manufacturability and scalability. In general, IPMC consists of an solid polyelectrolyte membrane and two surface electrode layers deposited with noble metal, such as Pt, Pd, Au, Ag, and carbon nanotube electrodes [6,7], resulting in a sandwich-like structure. Actuation performance of IPMC actuators is strongly affected by the surface electrode layers, especially for the electrical conductivity and the surface morphology [8-10].

Generally, surface electrode layers for IPMCs are prepared by two types of methods: vapor deposition, e.g. physical vapor deposition (sputtering, evaporation); and chemical reduction (electroless plating). Although the former is simple and fast, the surface adhesion between metal layers and polymer matrix is poor because there are no metal-polymer compositing layers. The latter method, meanwhile, can be utilized as forming compositing layers, resulting in stronger adhesion with the polyelectrolyte matrix [11]. However, the chemical method is time-consuming and shows poor repeatability because of several complex fabrication steps. Furthermore, the reduction agent can cause pollution and may be not good for human body. Thus, a new simple and environmentally-friendly

method for preparing noble electrodes of IPMC actuators is critically needed.

In recent decades, perfluorinate polymers as solid polyelectrolyte membrane have been successfully applied to both polymer actuators and fuel cell membranes [12,13]. However, owing to their several problems such as high price, gas permeability, and low thermal stability, various alternative polyelectrolyte membranes have been developed [14-16]. Among recently developed polyelectrolyte membranes, sulfonated polyimide (SPI) exhibits reliable mechanical strength, high thermal stability, high proton conductivity, and low price. Even though a series of SPI polyelectrolytes have been developed for high-performance fuel cell applications [17,18], so far they have not been applied to IPMC actuators. Recently, in-situ self-metallization method [19,20] has been developed to synthesize well-metallized polyimide membranes, offering processing simplicity and outstanding adhesion in the metal-polymer compositing layers.

In this study, we developed a facile synthesis approach to prepare an IPMC actuator based on sulfonated polyimide with silver electrodes using an in-situ self-metallization process.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

4, 4' - Oxidianiline(ODA, 97%), 3, 3' , 4, 4' - benzophenonetetracarboxylic dianhydride(BTDA, 96%) and Silver nitrate (99.8%) were purchased from Aldrich and without further purification. Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) were obtained Merck

Co., 2, 2'-Benzidinedisulfonic acid (BDSA) was obtained from Tokyo Chemical Industry Co.. The BDSA was titrated with aqueous lithium hydroxide, giving a lithium-containing BDSA (BDSA-Li) white powder which is soluble in dimethyl sulfoxide [21].

2.2 Synthesis of sulfonated poly (amic acid) (SPAA)

The synthesis of sulfonated poly (amic acid)(SPAA) was performed by first dissolving the diamine including BDSA-Li and ODA in DMSO and followed by addition of 1%(mol) offset dianhydride (BTDA) at ambient temperature. And then the reaction was continued for another 6h. SPAA was casted onto glass plate using a doctor blade set to obtain films with thickness ca. 140 μ m after restoring in oven at 30 $^{\circ}$ C for 10h. Half-dried SPAA films were carefully peeled from the glass plate.

2.3 Ionic exchange and self-metallization Process

The as-fabricated SPAA films were immersed into the 0.02 M aqueous [Ag(NH₃)₂]NO₃ solutions for about 8 min to perform ion exchange with silver ion. After washing with D.I. water and evaporating most of the water, the silver(I) doped membranes were thermally treated in an oven. The thermal circle involved heating over 1 to 150 $^{\circ}$ C and hold for 1 h, heating to 300 $^{\circ}$ C over 2 h and hold at 300 $^{\circ}$ C for additional 3 h. Thermal curing process cyclimidizes SPAA precursor to the SPI and simultaneously leading to the reduction of Ag⁺ to Ag particle, followed by a highly conductive Ag metal electrode layers. The total procedures are as shown in Figure 1.

Fig.1. Self-metallization of SPI via direct ionic exchange process.

3 Results and Discussion

To obtain a highly conductive Ag electrode, the diammino silver hydroxide cation (Ag[(NH₃)₂]OH) is used for the ionic exchange process as previously mentioned. The Ag loading was increased by 12.13 atom% because of not only carboxylic acid group but also the sulfonic acid group in SPAA matrix. The BDSA-Li was selected as the diamine instead of

BDSA-triethylamine because of its higher thermal stability for the self-metallization process at high temperature up to 300 $^{\circ}$ C [21,23]. In addition, the Li⁺ cations that bonded with sulfonic acid groups, can be directly applied to ion-migration under electrical field.

The ATR FT-IR spectra were measured with the PAA membranes before and after ionic exchange for understanding ion exchange process of SPAA with Ag salt. The peaks of stretching vibrations of carboxyl acid and amide I bond are located at 1712 and 1662 cm⁻¹, respectively. After the ion exchange process, a new peak is observed at 1377 cm⁻¹, as shown in Figure 2a, indicating the formation of a silver complex ligand through the ionic exchange process [19,22]. X-ray photoelectric spectra were also used for observation of the formed silver complex and its content as presented in Figure 2b. As for the PAA-Ag⁺, the binding energy at 367.2 and 373.0 eV is attributed to Ag3d 3/2 and Ag3d 5/2, respectively, indicating that the carboxyl acid group forms ionic pairs(-COO-Ag⁺) with Ag⁺.

Fig.2. (a) ATR-FTIR of SPAA and SPAA-Ag⁺, (b) XPS of SPAA-Ag⁺ and SPI-Ag.

Cross-sectional and surface SEM micrographs of the as-prepared SPI actuator were examined. Figure 3a, b show that silver electrodes were deposited on both sides of the SPI membrane, and energy dispersive spectrometer (EDS) analysis shows that sharp peaks assigned to Ag are observed on the surfaces of the SPI membrane. This further indicates that Ag particles tend to migrate to the surface of the SPI and form a conductive electrode layer. The measured surface resistance of the silver electrodes was 55.4 m Ω /sq as listed in Table 1. The high conductivity of the silver layers can improve the electromechanical performance of the SPI actuators.

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Table 1. Chemical and electrical properties of SPI

Sample	Water uptake (g/g)	Proton conductivity (S/cm)	Surface resistance (mΩ/sq)
SPI	0.182	0.017	55.4

In order to further observe the morphology of the silver electrodes, cross-sectional transmittance electronic microscopy (TEM) images were investigated, as shown in Figure 3c. The silver nanoparticles linked to form highly conductive electrodes. From the magnified image (Figure 3d), many nanoparticles act as “anchors”, located on the interface of the silver electrodes layers and the polymer matrix, resulting in strong adhesion between them. Moreover, the silver nanoparticles are dense and possess coagulated shapes, which is helpful for improving the actuation performance of the self-metallized SPI actuator.

Fig.3. (a) Cross-sectional SEM analysis of SPI-Ag, (b) Surface SEM image of SPI-Ag, (c) Cross-sectional TEM image and (d) magnification images of SPI-Ag.

The electromechanical performance is strongly affected by the morphology and electrical conductivity of the surface electrodes, as well as the basic properties of the polyelectrolyte matrix. The highly conductive silver electrodes formed via self-metallization can enhance the tip displacement of the cantilevered SPI actuator under the electrical stimuli. This actuator was fabricated by the thermal imidization of SPAA and simultaneous self-metallization of silver metal layer on both sides of membrane, as shown in Figure 4a. Figure 4b shows

the electromechanical performance of a self-metallized SPI actuator at the applied voltage of 0.5 V at 0.1 Hz under sinusoidal wave input. The tip displacement of the self-metallized SPI actuator reaches 1.2 mm under very low voltage excitation of 0.5 V.

Fig.4. (a) Photographs of SPI actuator, (b) Harmonic response of SPI actuator under sinusoidal electrical input of $0.5 \cdot \sin(2\pi \cdot 0.1 \cdot t)$.

4 Conclusion

In summary, highly conductive silver electrodes based on a sulfonated polyimide was newly prepared through a facile method for IPMC actuator. A strong adhesion at the metal-polymer interface was maintained via self-metallization. The bending actuation of the self-metallized SPI actuator under sinusoidal electrical input shows large harmonic response. The SPI described herein is believed to be a new ionic polymer metal composite actuator for artificial muscles.

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